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Cimicomorpha: Nabidae: *Nabis americanoferus*

Nabidae? Costa Rica
Cimicomorpha

Nabidae?:

Puntarenas, Costa Rica

basally, scP. goes under \mathcal{R}

basally, MA and MP are adjacent, not fused into a stem!

Cimicomorpha: Reduviidae, genus undet., FW base, Costa Rica, black & ugly

Cimicomorpha, Reduviidae, Harpactorinae, *Heza* sp., FW & HW bases

Cimicomorpha, Reduviidae, Harpactorinae, *Heza* sp., FW & HW, Costa Rica

Reduviidiidae

black ugly mama

eclis costal break?
flexible zone

AA 3+4 Added to remigium!
anal lobe starts at anal fold
(instead of at claval flexion line!)

Cimicomorpha Tingidae

Costa Rica

ScP goes under R!
epipleuron present!
(PC extends ventrad under ant. margin)

Dipsocoridae: *Cryptostemma*

Dipsocoridae: *Cryptostemma incurvatum*

Ceratocombidae: *Ceratocombus* sp.

SCP basally joins under R

Dipso *Schizopteridae encrusiladanannus*

Schizopteridae
Schizoptera sp.

Enico *Embolorrhinus leleupi*

FW Enicocephalidae: *Embolorrhynus leleubi*

HW Enicocephalidae: *Embolorrhynus leleupi*

FW Enicocephalidae: *Embolorrhynus leleupi*

F Cu reduced?

wildly derived/reduced articulation
(see next FW for comparison)

Enico Stenopirates

FW Enicocephalidae: *Embolearhinus leleupi*

HW Enicocephalidae: *Embolerrhinus leleupi*

Enicocephalidae: *Embolerrhinus leleupi*

Heteroptera Gerro *Gerris remigis*

FW Gerromorpha: *Gerris remigis*

Gerromorpha: *Macrovelia hornii*

Gerromorpha: *Paravelia prachialis*

Saldidae Costa Rica

FW

Saldidae

Australia

plesiomorphic: Progonocymicidae
Pelocidiidae

FW

Belostomatidae

Costa Rica

FW Belostomatidae: *Lethocerus* ?

Costa Rica

HW

Belostomatidae: *Lethocerus*?

Costa Rica

Nepomorpha, Belostomatidae, *Lethocerus* sp., HW base; Costa Rica

HW Belostomatidae: *Lethocerus* sp.
(FW not figured) Honduras

Nepomorpha, Belostomatidae, *Lethocerus* sp., HW base; Costa Rica

medial plate (F of M & Cu) appears reduced

Nepomorpha, Belostomatidae, *Lethocerus* sp., FW base; Costa Rica

Nepomorpha, Belostomatidae, *Lethocerus* sp., FW base; Costa Rica

Nepomorpha, Belostomatidae, *Lethocerus?* sp., FW base; Costa Rica

Nepomorpha

Nepidae: *Nepa apiculata*

Nepomorpha
Notonecta irrorata

Nepomorpha, Ochteridae, *Ochterus caffer*, FW

Nepomorpha, Ochteridae, *Ochterus caffer*, HW

Belostomatidae

Lethocerus? Costa Rica

Pentatomomorpha Coreidae: *Anas armigera*

Pentatomomorpha, Coreidae, genus undet.; Costa Rica

identification of branches uncertain

Synapomorphies: (AA₁₊₂ is mostly Cost)
 AA is partially reduced and added to remigium. Therefore, Anal lobe starts at anal fold and contains only AP: in Blatto, Hemi, Emdoneoptera

Synplesiomorphy: in Pleconeoptera and Orthoneoptera, anal lobe starts at claval flexion line and contains AA₁₊₂, AA₃₊₄, AP₁₊₂, AP₃₊₄

Pentatomorpha Coreidae: *Anas armigera*

Pentatomomorpha: Coreidae: *Pephricus livingstoni*

Wings overlap, left wing is longer
membrane translucent, veins darkly pigmented
Body length 10 cm
prothoracic lobes are homologous with winglets
abdominal lobes are folded epicoxae

Pentatomomorpha

Coreidae: *Pephricus livingstoni*

Zrutpan, Transvaal
South Africa

Heteroptera, Pentatomorpha, Scutelleridae, genus undet;
 Costa Rica, large, yellow with black dots

In FW distal third: veinal identity is uncertain

